

DYMAN

DYNAMICALLY MANAGED SELF-COOLING
HPC DATA CENTERS

DYMAN is a three-year EIC Pathfinder Challenges project that brings together 11 partners from five countries (Spain, Germany, Italy, Belgium and Turkey)

DYMAN aims to revolutionize the cooling sector by advancing two core concepts:

- the integration of two-phase flow in adsorption chillers based on new low-temperature materials for sorption cooling
- a new way of active management of the data centre integrating the cooling system as part of the optimization of processor management.

DYMAN will develop pioneering solutions to reduce the impact of thermal energy management in HCP installations and data server rooms. These solutions will be **tested** on a virtual commissioning level and a short-term physical test **in two HPC facilities**: the **Barcelona Supercomputing Center** (Barcelona, Spain) and the **HPC4AI at University of Torino** (Turin, Italy).

The inefficiency of standard adsorption chillers and water network complexities hindered achieving the desired energy efficiency. As data centres' cooling demand continues to rise, alternative solutions are needed. DYMAN targets the development of a completely new design of adsorption **chillers** based on the following innovations:

- ✓ Low-temperature adsorbents that achieve high capacities at very low conduction temperatures below 50 °C.
- ✓ New adsorption heat exchangers made with 3D printed structures that integrate the adsorption material into a porous structure, reducing the internal thermal resistance.
- ✓ Two-phase cooling for high-performance computing servers to handle thermal loads more efficiently from next-generation processors.
- ✓ A new type of adsorption cooling system integration in the data centre environment.
- ✓ A new form of active data centre management integrating the cooling system as part of the optimisation of processor management by providing an ontology based on an AI-assisted approach to O&M practices.

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<https://dyman-project.eu/>

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